

12:30 - 14:00	Session 6: Relating the Dark Matter Density Field to Galaxy Properties	Chair: Lorenzo Zanisi (Univ. of Southampton)
12:30 - 13:00	6a Invited Talk: Casey Papovich (Texas A&M)	Invited talk
13:00 - 13:15	6b Mariko Kubo (Ehime Univ)	Protocluster survey/characterization with NGRST
13:15 - 13:30	6c Song Huang (Princeton)	Connecting the Bright and Dark Sides of Massive Galaxies in the Universe
13:30 - 13:45	6d Jenna Samuel (UCD)	Predictions for satellite galaxy distributions around Milky Way analogs with NGRST
13:45 - 14:00	6e Scott Chapman (UBC)	Massive Galaxy Protoclusters in the Early Universe uncovered by the South Pole Telescope

Session 6 live captioning on Wednesday, 7 October 2020

Casey Papovich: ...Provides rare objects which now we have samples from our data this will allow us to tell you those on a similar setting, and easily identify those objects. I will give some examples throughout the talk, they will include things like recently quenched galaxies. They will include galaxies and very high density environment such as galaxy clusters, mergers, and then we'll have samples. At the same time send statistics is no longer going to be a significant obstacle we will have to be very cognizant of the systematics in the data. What that means is very careful planning will have to go into the sample and having large enough samples that we can provide almost systematics. I think Roman will do that as well because we will provide large enough samples that we can do self calibrations for example. Okay. To motivate this, but I want to spend some time on is talking about what we are learning from humble now and what on the frontier we can do, primarily with the capabilities and the infrared graph. This is one of those areas where I think no one anticipated that it would be contributing in this area. No one really thought about it as a spectrograph when they launched it. What we have come to realize is that when you're working and space and your way from the terrestrial background, we have much greater ability to measure and very accurate flux with Spectra, using the facial resolution rate of course Roman will provide this as well. I will talk about what we have been doing both with galaxies quenched and the work we are trying to do there. I will talk about how it proceeds within galaxies as well as how quenching or star formation proceeds in different environments. I will talk about what we can learn and the metal production and feedback with the studies from the omission line. To do this I am going to use a survey we been working on, it's a tested acronym, candles, a mission re-ionization survey. It originally targeted the mission, but it's a whole range of science. Cycle 20 something, Hubble program with 12 depth, one of two observations and six pointing with North and South as illustrated in the image below. This can be combined then with the spectroscopy and they cover 25 microns which is very similar to the range we can expect from the Roman telescope, prism data though. The resolution, G1 data has provided the resolution, it is -- these are comparable to the, what will be enabled by some of the work that you will see presented here today. You can envision would be enabled by the observations just on a more massive scale. While I'm not going to talk about that, other people have been talking about how Roman observations may be able to get the mission and what we can learn about it and I will refer back to some of

the earlier talks. And also Isaac Young has -- I'm sorry, they have a poster at the session. That is the link that is provided there. Okay. What do we get? With the data that is provided we can obtain spectra like this or at least there is a different region of optical Emission from galaxy witches here. Primarily I will use this to talk about two different ways we can study galaxy. On the left I'm showing one dimensional spectrum for stellar populations that have been red shifted out to what you see there about 1.2, 1.3, top from bottom there on the left. This is shown at the resolution of the G1. This is what you can expect from the low resolution we get from Hubble and eventually from a Roman. Indicated on their are some of the common absorption features that people are using for work on galaxies, potential populations including delta, the other feature that are indicated. Very common features that show things that. It shows what is present from ionized gas as a function of red shift on the bottom. Working out of these redshifts become a 1-2 come when you cover all the transitions you know and love including oxygen two, oxygen three, Alpha, which is blended with nitrogen two. Spectra looked like this. This is a composite of galaxy spectra shifted over combining the data format galaxies at 1.1, 2.3 in different stellar mass and integrated here. You can see these strong nebular mission features are easy to detect, especially here. We can see the features are there to enable studies like Metallicity and gas ionization. We will use these features so we can understand property. The first one I want to talk about is when two massive galaxies quench? What can we do they are. Primarily this works, the thesis who is graduating this year. His first project was looking at how well we can use prism data taken from the telescope to measure the population and constrain the parameters. To illustrate the process he was working with galaxies, selected to have very little star formation between one and 1.8 with a stellar mass greater than ten. To model their Spectra he starts at a very high resolution model illustrated here. He ruins it by involving it with the galaxy morphology and then forward modeling on what it will look like. And from that we can extract to the very, infinite signal to noise spectrum of this stellar population model. He does this over a large grid bearing parameters such as red shift, stellar population, history, Metallicity. Here's an example of one of these objects. The spectrum in the middle shows the blue points there are the extracted data for one of our galaxies. This is just the data and the models are fed only against that to illustrate what we can get just from the G1 oh two data from itself. The red line is not the best, it's a medium where we take the most likely parameter value of the different population, Metallicity, et cetera to see what the population would look like. It's remarkable it fits them very well. You will see that in the illustration. This particular model has an age come a light weighted age of around 2 billion years. Metallicity turns out to be about 90% solar where the two dimensional series are illustrated there on the right to. We can do this for a much larger range of galaxy. I want to talk about the Metallicity. When we plotted these up, our data points are the symbols here. 1.1-1.6, the blue, orange, green, red circles. The large symbols. We compare what we get for those galaxy examples from a 1-1.6. We find that they primarily want to have the solar Metallicity, but a time period in the universe that is eight, nine, billion years in the past. We compare those to what they find at .7 and other data sets and we find there's been remarkably little evolution for galaxy in this relationship. It implies that these galaxies that form to their early, they formed it earlier, before the time we served them. They're already up in the solar value. One thing I find remarkable is when you look at the gas diagram shown here, stellar mass, x-axis, and then the Metallicity derived from the oxygen line on the Y axis, the equivalent of that. There are plenty of nebular objects, but when we look at higher redshifts, the data shown, there are few of these as the stellar mass as are talking about. One of the things we have to do is connect the high stellar Metallicity we see in these galaxies, their populations, compared to the gas Metallicity that people are seeing, or in the same mass. They seem to be very rare. We have yet to identify the galaxy with the objects we see. Let's illustrate that here by summarizing this little portion. The first few points they are, whatever I stated and what I would like to know, where is the galaxy we are seeing greater than one now? I will leave it with a question, is solar Metallicity that we see a cause of it? That is something we are trying to explore now, but want more time to talk about that. This has been diligently working through the rest of our data sets. He has updated the message to include not just the data, but other agency spectra as we have combining with the broadband. He's managed to do that right I will fit them with a star formation histories, with some of the work you heard in this morning session as well about how we can arrive there somehow. I'm showing results now from three of the objects and the example. We began at a very low current level of star formation, Wolin, 1.2, 1.3. And the bottom shows some of panel shows the rhythm data, the blue and the right here at 1.1. Where this plot shows the derived star formation history we are getting. This illustrates these three cases, different kinds of star formation history. We have one where the galaxies observed at this end of the plot and then have very quiescent for a long time. Very sudden quenching. That is what they indicated. Other objects we have constant star formation and then a steady decline or less constant. We are able to derive these constraints, I will point you to this poster here, here's a link in the Slack channel, but you can find it under poster. He's using 100 galaxies, driving the star formation history and then finding correlations. That's very interesting and I encourage you to go see. The next portion of the talk I would like to focus on how we are using

spatially resolved information that we get from the spectroscopy. This is a nice paper written, using 3D data, where the top plot shows the two dimensional spectrum which is a nice dispersed spectra of the galaxy. There is this region here where you model what the continuum looks like, you model that and subtract it, you are left with part of the Emission associated with alpha nebular emission in this galaxy. The direction, the direction contain spatial information. A one-dimensional spatial flight. Including spatial information. This is one you have only one position angle. We did this for our data set, we observed multiple angles. The nice spiral galaxy. You can see three different position angles, the stellar continuum is the easiest. You will notice this here, associated with the Emission but you notice it rotates. And we can use this one dimensional slices of all different rotation angle, put it back together and make a map of where the emission of the compare it to the directive. And now we have really two dimensional spatially aligned to maps and our sample. That has Hubble like resolution. Of course Roman will give more data. We can use this to understand where the various properties are occurring in the star formation and then also Metallicity, all of the other features. Nelson did this in a pioneering experiment where this is showing stacks of galaxies, .7-1.1. And she was looking at where the L formation occurs, what that apology looks like seen here. And what she found for her sample, 1-1.7 is that primarily the size indicated here in blue, it's at least as large as the stellar continuum or larger as you go to high mass. On average it's about 1.1 times larger. This has been repeated for high mass galaxies, another paper by Wilman, focusing on the higher mass of the distribution. We are able to measure it. Sort of pioneering, there going in and inside fashion because it is tracing the stellar mass, the elephant is tracing where it is occurring. It's a larger radii, that means we are finding alpha in the outskirts. We started looking at this in our own data sets. We are showing individual measurements now of alpha versus the continuum. You can see we are tracing the star-forming regions in the galaxy. Surprisingly when we look at these we find very little difference between the alpha Emission and the blue point in this plot, the x-axis, and the size of the emission compared to the continuum which is shown in red. The distributions are in the middle, no statistical difference between these two. We are looking at a very higher mass object, but something worth looking into. It may also imply there is a change as we go from higher on the lower and how galaxies grow. Some of the fundamental questions we need to explore. It will help us see the variations that we are seeing in these objects. Another thing that were looking at is somewhere between one and less than one we know that the effects of environmental mass are no longer severable. They been studying this by looking at the size of star-forming galaxies and clusters and comparing them to the field. Which you can even see in the images, the alpha Emission is much more compact than the continuum. When she looks at that she finds, yes, statistically you can determine that. Here is illustrated in the fact that the continuum sizes are larger on average and the L5 sizes with blue points and both plots. It seems to be implying that there is evidence in the high density environment galaxy clusters were outside quench, meaning the stellar continuum is larger than where the star formation as occurring on the inside. What I will point out here though is that these statistics, their little bleak in terms of what we can do now. On average we have only a few objects per cluster that you can study in this fashion and clearly we are very statistically limited if that's a word. I will leave with a couple of questions here. Conclusions and questions. We are able to get from the prism data, there is evidence for inside-out quenching among massive field galaxies, but that is not the case and cluster galaxies. It seems to be some environmental impact. That is where our statistics are too limited to get at the heart of that matter. Whereas the red shift, around .5, there is less evidence for any difference in the size as compared to starlight. We see galaxies are not primarily growing inside, why and we are exploring the physics there. Okay. The last 5 minutes I would like to talk about what else we can learn from the emission line, primarily I'm going to be doing that using observations of strong emission lines and mapping these objects. Just to give you an illustration of what we can do with this, this is close to zero. There results where they're able your multifiber, making these maps where they trace out the locations of oxygen, data and they're able to produce for example Metallicity maps and identify where the metal are bred here you're seeing on the left, the image of the galaxy with the MaNGA spiral bundle hexagon. And on the right you have the Metallicity map associated with these galaxies. Where writer colors correspond to higher metals. Primarily we begin to see that galaxy has more metals and their outskirts and they have less -- sorry, more metals and their center and then the Metallicity begins to drop. This was measured for the first time by the collaborator and 2017. They show a plot here showing the Metallicity on the Y axis as a function of the distance from the center towards galaxies where they have averaged stellar mass spirit what they find is that it is relatively flat for low mass galaxies. They show low radiance. Most of the metals come it's a very strong move towards the outskirts. It sets up this idea that if we are seeing galaxies form, where are there metals distributed? This tells us something about where they form and how they end up where they are. Science has been working on this with the data, he's been using maps like the ones we see appear at the top. We are showing oxygen to, nebular emission, oxygen three, and from that were able to construct a very similar kinds of metal a city maps for galaxies. Two examples illustrated here, they correspond to the map at the top were on the left we have a idle rich

center as is shown here on purple and on the outskirts. The other wants inverted where we have the metal center and Rich on the outskirts. These are two examples to show the data. I will show these plots, you will see them. We will give you an idea of what we are looking at. The Y axis is the Metallicity gradients, the change in the oxygen abundance as a function of radius. That is what were looking at. Today's galaxies are found down here. That was the result we had from MaNGA. We had negative gradients. And then, that means you would be more metal rich and the inner parts and if you're in the upper part of this diagram that makes you more metal rich and the outer part. Okay. What we find primarily, and this is the compilation of literature points, not quite 100 data points from the literature combined with 254 galaxies, primarily the galaxies are associated with very flat gradient. There are some evidence that galaxies have some gradient, but by largely majority do not. There's very little spatial gradient. Very little tendency function. In terms of statistics, most of these are flat, 10% declining, I will refer that to Raymond's paper. If you compare this to what we find at zero, this median, we find its very flat. If you look at the stellar mass, they're dropping. What this is telling us, these lack of gradients in these galaxies mean they are very efficient redistribution of metals. The higher gas dispersion, higher outflows, it's keeping the Metallicity very smooth. The last point I want to make with this, when we look at this kind of plot, there are indications of galaxies that have positive gradients. These are often called inverted gradients. This is work we see here. This implies that in the centers of the galaxies they have a lower metallicity than I do in the outskirts. There were some other work by collaborators, it shows this nicely by using the lens galaxies, very rare, only a few of these that you can do this with. Gravitational magnified by a factor of 6.35. On the right is a similar kind of metallicity where it's a lower metallicity in the core versus the outskirts. These inverted gradients say something interesting, it may mean you're seeing the signs of the unpolluted gas created into the nuclei, being enriched through star formation. This is something where I think we can work through in the future to understand how this process works better and what it means for both accretion and for feedback. The problem is we are very limited. Just to summarize, all of those, what does it mean for the Roman Space Telescope? This'll be my final slide. The problem is that the current samples we have at Hubble while great or small. All studies I talked about we have between 30 and 300 galaxies total in every one of those studies, these require more than 100 spaces. We need to build up these statistics, we are still very limited by this. We don't know what the interesting variations are. In addition to that we need to understand our control, comparing samples taken to different objects and different depths. All of this can get mitigated. Just to give you another illustration of this, we have these galaxies at one and we have tens of those. We have very few kinds of those options. There are rare and we need them to understand a variation is in the sample. In addition do have a statistic to control. I will leave you with a slide. If only we had a telescope with the power of Hubble that had the ability to do this much more efficiently, for example Roman. I will leave this bottoms light up which illustrates this point. We have showed two of the images taken as part of the frontier initiative, compared to what you can gain from Roman. It would allow for studies of cluster core and then an enormous range of area to sample all at once the full range of environment and these objects. I look forward to that. I think I will stop there and I will be happy to take any questions.

Great talk. The metallicity relation, evolution or lack thereof to be different for diverse environments. Perhaps a faster way is metallicity from high to low.

I think that's a great question. This is where the statistics would be very useful. Certainly there is some indication that environment has affected the evolution of galaxy, both the star formation history and the enrichment. I think you would expect to see that. That is somewhere where I think we had something like Roman. I think I would expect to see that, but if someone knows more about that they're welcome to comment.

Okay. I just want to let you know, you have quite a number of questions and I encourage you to go to the slack channel and take a look at those and begin a dialogue there.

We are now, **Mariko Kubo**. She will tell us about cluster with the Roman Space Telescope. You have 12 minutes and I will give you a warning.

Mariko: Okay. I am Mariko Kubo. I'm excited to host this exciting workshop. As pointed out in many presentations, and very unique science. I will talk about the survey on the characterization. Here I will show the image, first I will talk about the, our current study of the statistics by using the telescope. And then I will talk about the prospect.

Protoclusters, into galaxies -- interesting to study how galaxies in their environment and -- we also test were cosmological structure model. We know that the galaxies have already -- there protoclusters are over two, they are important to characterize the properties. What I want to show, the variation. In the universe, they dominate the, it's a necessary piece to understand galaxy formation and evolution. There are many studies for protoclusters. We now know that protoclusters have a wide range of properties and the criteria is not so uniform. We should know the typical evolution stage of protoclusters to perform this we need the survey. And in addition, properties -- over three. Then we need multi-wavelength observations. Now we are studying protoclusters. Maybe you know that it is a prime focus and each have -- 1.77, nine moons or. Now we take a survey, the program survey. This is our survey in three years. This is our -- there are already many studies in various areas. May be next to speakers it has come up in the presentation. HSC SSP, investigation for future survey. Now systematic protocol survey. This is -- a leader or the survey. In the area you can see the largest protocluster of 4 and the deep blue area, we can obtain the protocluster. The protocluster challenges us to -- the number. The selection criteria is set systematically based on the cosmological, numerical. Based on this criteria, massive cluster through the dash this shows the distribution of protoclusters in the survey. At this point, 180 protoclusters, 121. This is a close up here. Here we see the largest systematic protoclusters. There is this large auto cluster, we study the nature of galaxies. A candidate on the function. Here I'm going to talk about the properties. With this, we can also show the property. Here we use the data. The special resolution on the data is not enough to identify the galaxy, but by searching with 180 protoclusters, protocluster. We also use that. We show the top -- galaxies -- we can constrain the four by using this. This is the protoclusters, we successfully detect infrared. This is some of our results. We show the protocluster based on that. It shows that a strong galaxy. The red shows the galaxy in protocluster, corresponding to -- the protocluster. This indicates the galaxies -- statistic. It is also interesting that it is different from the galaxy. The temperature of the protocluster is very high -- the origin. At this point we cannot infer the dash but we can see that we need the obscure. This is so many of the protocluster survey. We successfully had it. Now the confirmation, also is ongoing. We show the environmental dependence in protocluster. Rest frame luminous are not an over dense regions. Here we show that there is a significant obscured star formation on AGN in the protocluster. Here we show the evolution of the star formation protocluster. You have 2 minutes. Okay. Here we show the results with the infrared cluster. There are many uncertainties, but I believe it continues involving -- our results -- questions. First, statistical study at the four and at the four. Also further characterization of galaxies and protoclusters. In our case we wanted to separate the contribution of AGN. To characterize protocluster members across cosmic time, deep and wide infrared, it is necessary. The Roman telescope is very feasible for future protocluster study. This is the final slide. Here we show the survey, this is just -- one survey. We can perform the vital survey for protoclusters and it with the telescope we can survey protoclusters with the epoch, also based on the distant red, stellar mass. We can study the assembly on the morphology. Identifying -- it is very powerful tool for the protocluster. We covered the survey earlier, but it is very feasible. Not for protoclusters, but there are some for the infrared. Here they perform the infrared. The Roman Space Telescope, 100 times for the protocluster. Ten times deeper. This study with the infrared, -- also future. This can only be performed with the combination of the survey. That is all. Thank you.

Great. Thank you. when I bent over but but that is fine. This was very exciting. I have one question myself. You mentioned that some of the clusters are already being followed up, if I recall correctly, have you any insight on that? I mean, you said there were some clusters if I recall correctly, in a previous line. Yes. -- the observation, the discovery for the protocluster. Okay. I guess, add another question as well. These protoclusters, have you looked into data for x-ray which may be helpful to detect AGN? May be data -- we have not yet seen the data, but maybe it is very feasible to see the other data. Okay. Thank you very much for the talk. I'm looking forward to seeing the results.

We welcome our third speaker today which is **Song Huang** from Princeton. He will give us some insight about how to connect dark matter and stars using observations. Thank you.

Song: Great. Thank you for organizing this conference. It's exciting to be here. My name is Song Huang. I'm at Princeton and I've been working with the survey collaboration for the past five years. Today I'm going to share something we hear about the galaxy. Before we do that I want to leave you the general message I have. I believe -- the first advantage is we should pay more attention to low surface brightness. We can discover in the larger topics with stellar Halo, title feature, and low surface dwarfs. All of this has been popular in recent years, but we know very

little about them. It is really challenging. I believe Roman has a unique position to improve this and I encourage you to look at the posters and other thoughts in this conference. The second matter, don't forget about the dark side. Don't forget about the dark light Halo. for people starting the evolution, and grows and merges with the halo. We cannot look at the information without understanding that. On this topic, they will have a remarkable revolution I. I want to give the big picture, I want to convince you that we are actually entering a new era of the connection. Here's a plot that I compiled and recently published the stellar Halo mass of different data. As you can see here, the good news is in general they agree. I would like to point out that we do have some problems at the high mass end. Here, this massive galaxy create some of the most massive dark matter halo in the universe. These halos are uniquely important for formation. It's really important for us to understand the connection better. I would like to point out that the difficulty is not only just that it's a dark matter halo mass, but it's also about the stellar mass. It's very difficult with the mass of galaxies to do that. Such complexity, in recent years have been broadly described where in phase one you have very intense dissipation, and the quenching process that creates the dense core. And this is something, and after that is quenched, the mergers take over and build up the halo. Today, a huge part of the halo is actually in the low surface. That is it's very hard to observe and present a great challenge in studying the galaxies. Also this part is super important because it's dominated by the stars. It is important for the record and may be has a closer connection. To give you a demonstration of this, here's a three color picture taken from the meter telescope. We can already see there are several massive galaxy and a lot more around it. Everything seems fine until you take a deeper look. Here's the same thing using the meter. And now immediately you can see all of the low surface features a round mass of galaxies and it becomes much more. We can cover a more reliable from all these galaxies. We have a more complete picture. We can map the solution all the way, and it can really improve our understanding of this galaxy. Here I will quickly show you what we recently have. First question is about the evolution of stellar mass functions. In recent years we noted there is a problem as the function, basically if you are looking, there is generally a lack of evolution in the last 5-6 years. This is very puzzling, all of it continues to merge with smaller galaxies into their halos. We realize that it's a deeper image, it recovers more stellar mass. Now actually we have, we can recover a lot more and we believe that is much more reliable as the total. This will help us understand the function. In addition to the stellar mass, we were able to -- the one-dimensional, all the way to almost 100. Here I show you the surface density profiles of the galaxy with 2.2-2.5. I also show the median. The first we can see, there is a huge scatter in the profile. I hope I can convince you that the high quality, we know that it's intrinsic, so it causes to highlight the structural diversity in the galaxies and we flag the merger. And it's also worth pointing out that we see no distinction between the so-called normal or the CD galaxy. Basically there is a continuous profile that reflects a wider range in the scatter halo. As I show here color-coded between ten and 150. We can see that more massive galaxies tend to have a more prominent halo, a shallower profile, while the inner profile is similar. The inner part has a different parent also, we can see this image as we look into the two dimensional shape of this. Here I will show it is projected profile from the same sample and allow us to have the profile from the same three. We immediately learn that actually there is where the massive galaxy, the halo becomes the second point is that we also see there is the increasing part where basically more massive galaxies tend to have a more -- we think this is a very interesting and it may be related to the intrinsic shape of the dark mellow stomach matter halo. I also wanted to point out, the last speaker, there was a profile of the metallicity profile in the technique. This actually showed that this subtle profile will wash out -- that is why we need to rely on deep image of individual galaxy. It will help us understand massive galaxies, we have to remember that the galaxy with a massive dark matter halo, easily 21. There also incredible -- within this region that can coherently -- and if we can carefully, we can obtain the so-called galaxy. A typical merriment, basically a come almost with a total mess of massive galaxy. A great deal of information about the solution dark matter halo mass, environment, and the halo. Generally speaking, more massive halo suit have a higher amplitude profile. With the help of this, now we can look at the connection between the distribution and halo mass. Here we group the massive galaxy with similar of three groups with different solutions. 2 minutes. The green ones showing different profile. On the right side I show that the same profile and you can see that they leave the dark matter halo with different mass where the red ones have more prominent halos. I want to point out that it's very different. On the galaxy side -- this is the picture that is interesting. With help of the capability, we can see the halo mass by including the solutions. Here we will build an empirical model that will describe the halo mass on not only the total mass, but also the -- Y-axis. On the two plots we use the underlying color and to the to highlight a trend. Again, we see this trend that has the same stellar mass, more prominent stellar halo. Using this galaxy lensing capability we can also categorize halo mass relation and evaluate it to the dark side. Here I show the difference definitions in the upper panel and a different definition. What we see here is the hello mass with number density being used in different halo mass proxies. And it's basically from lower halo mass. It generally means it's there. From this general, we learned that -- they don't really care that much about the

dark matter halo which is interesting. More interesting we see that even compared to the total mass, they have a closer relation as they have smaller and their halo mass. We believe a lot of interesting in the future. Compared to that, it has a wider survey with infrared capability. It has a great -- You need to start concluding. 13 minutes now. Okay. I will just -- I think it has the capability, infrared imaging. With the capabilities and combination with the data can really help us and of course the high-resolution is also improving a lot. Combine all of this, I believe that they can use a massive galaxy to tackle a lot of important questions in both galaxy formation and halo connection. And how I use this galaxy to identify halos and use them to start cosmology. Thank you very much.

Thank you. This was extremely interesting. I work on this stuff. I really appreciated the talk. There are a couple of questions on slack. What is a typical red shift of your examples? And do you see any signs of red shift evolution?

Be go that's a very good question. Our sample is with the resolution, so right now we are exploring that from 0-0.5. That's not tiny, but also the survey covers only a few hundred. It's not large enough. We look into that, but we see no trend right now, but it's with uncertainty. We believe with Roman we can really help us review any potential.

Okay. Since we are out of time I would encourage you to go over to slack. There are some other interesting questions there. We thank you again.

We are going with our next speaker who is **Jenna Samuel** from UCD. She will tell us about predictions for satellite galaxy in the Milky Way. You will have a two-minute warning. Whenever you are ready you can start. Thank you.

Jenna: Thank you Lorenzo. Like you mentioned, my name is Jenna Samuel and I am a finishing graduate student at UC Davis where I work with my advisor analyzing the fire simulation along with the rest of our group which you can see here. This is what we look like these days. Today I'm going to tell you about some of my work looking specifically at the facial and kinematic distributions of satellite galaxies around Milky Way analogs and fire simulation and from comparisons to local group observations as well as some predictions for the Roman Space Telescope. First up, I want to tell you about the sample of simulations that I use in my research. The first simulation that I used was run by my advisor Andrew Wetzel, eight separate simulations containing isolated Milky Way mass galaxy. I also use the suite, local volumes and simulation. It's three separate simulations that each contain two Milky Way and are 31 designed to match the local group. You can see images from both of the simulations. You can see the more morphology galaxies line up pretty well with what we observed at the local group for the Milky Way and are 31. You can also notice that our host galaxies are surrounded by rail by realistic populations of satellite galaxies. It is these galaxies that have been the focus of my work so far. In particular, why am I interested, looking at how they line up with some of the problems that we might see with the satellite work galaxies. Namely these are the missing satellite problems, dark matter simulations have predicted far too many satellites in the vicinity of Milky Way halos compared to observation. Many simulations, many simulations are now claiming that there is no missing satellite problem and we want to just confirm that as well. In addition to extending that analysis and looking at not just the total number of satellites within the radius, but also their distribution as a function of distance from the host galaxy. Finally, going to the 3D kinematic spatial distribution, I've been interested in addressing the satellite plane problems as observed. So why are the distributions of the satellite galaxy and the local group interesting to begin with? If we look at the number of satellite galaxies contained within a given distance as a function, we see that around the Milky Way, they have very similar radio profiles with 150. However, if we look beyond that from 152300, we see that the profiles around the Milky Way diverge significantly. We want to look into our simulation to see if we can bracket this observed range profile. Indeed we do. Here on the right-hand side now I am plotting and calling, the radio profile across all of the host as well as over time from 0-0.1. On top of that I am plotting the median local group profile. You can see that the color simulation region nicely stands between both the Milky Way distribution and M31 distribution. 300K PC, match any total number of observed satellites and as a function of distance all the way down to small distances we see that we are matching up with a number of satellites. This is important because it's not just the physics and our simulation, but how we are resolving the galaxies close to the host where they often disrupted and destroyed. We are also predicting that with the Milky Way analogs outside of local groups that most of them will have between 11 and 27 satellite galaxies within 300 KPC. We are claiming it's no longer a problem as well as resolving the satellite galaxies around. This still leaves open the question of whether or not the full 3D distribution of satellite galaxies and kinematic

distribution match up with local group observations where we observe satellite. And so if you're not familiar with the satellite problem in the local group, this is basically defined as the observed spatial flattening and kinematic experience of satellite galaxies around the Milky Way and to the lesser extent around 31. As it pans around, you can see that the Milky Way satellites are highly taken to a thin spatial plane and the green emanating from that shows the average satellite momentum direction. Because it's perpendicular to the satellite plane itself, that indicates that the satellites are actually orbiting coherently, so they have a line orbit within that dense satellite plane. It is not something that is generally seen and it's one of the reasons why people have referred to this as a problem. In order to investigate the problem in our simulation and make accurate comparisons between simulations and observation we have chosen two different metrics to characterize satellite planes in both emulation and observation. Here I am showing one spatial metric, basically characterizes the thickness of the satellite plane. On the right-hand side I'm showing the characterizing how a a line the orbits are by each satellite by getting the angular deviation of their individual momentum from the average satellite factor shown as the long arrow. I will demonstrate here these two metrics, the Milky Way satellite. You can see the satellite plan and these two images here and you can see it's flattened and that most of the Milky Way satellites have aligned orbited. If you look into the simulations in order to measure the satellite plane metrics and also to measure them on the Milky Way, these are the main results that we get. Here I am plotting the Milky Way values for the height as well as the distribution in the simulation across 0-0.2. What was immediately apparent is that the Milky Way is very spatially flattened compared to our simulation and it also has a very tight distribution reflecting small uncertainties on the Milky Way satellite position. While the satellite planes are rare in our simulations they do occur in 1% of our Snapchat. Because we have such explicit kinematic data for Milky Way proper motion, we can also measure the 3D dispersion for the Milky Way in addition to the simulation. However the Milky Way proper motion uncertainties are much longer than positional uncertainties and you can see that reflected in the larger spread on the Milky Way. In the kinematic space we see 5% of our simulation actually has the Milky Way like planes. While most are rare, they do occur. And beyond just checking for the instance of Milky Way planes and our simulation we also wanted to investigate about what are the underlying causes of satellite planes? The most interesting result that we found in this investigation is that it really matters whether or not you have a massive satellite in your center. Here is the same thought essentially as the previous slide except now I'm splitting up the sample into the companions near the center shown in red versus all of the other simulations shown in blue. You can immediately see that the presence of a companion rarely increases the likelihood of measuring a Milky Way like plane by a factor of 2.5. And so with my work from my first paper and in the satellite planes that should be out in the archive next week, we think we have gone a long way to addressing the missing satellite planes, missing satellite problem in addition to resolving the distribution of satellite galaxies around their host and even looking for securities with the distribution that we see in the local group. However, it remains to be seen whether or not the Milky Way is an outlier in terms of a general observed population. And so they surveys actually go a long way to increasing the sample size of analogs as well as satellites around the analogs. 2 minutes. Thank you. About 100 systems total. We know that it is going to increase our sample even further and because of its large field of view will likely be able to image the full region and get a sample of all satellite galaxies with a zero radius we also know that from earlier talks this week, for the most nearby Milky Way analogs, we will be able to get distances to those analogs as well as their satellites which might give us some 3D positional information for satellite galaxies. Some of the results I presented and three already can be applied to observations with the Roman Space Telescope, but in the survey we have only satellite positions and projection, I have the analysis with 2D as well. And so here I am showing 2D, this is just a height measured and projection along 1,000 lines of sight. You are saying distribution along the lines of sight for both observations as Milky Way as well is in our simulation. Immediately it's apparent that looking along many lines of sight has the effect of increasing the total height and broadening the distributions of both observations and simulations. Another effect of this is that the Milky Way is no longer quite so plain compared to the simulation and its distribution is quite broad. If we extend this further into a 2D where we characterize the kinematic coherent value and velocities by counting up the percentage that share the same direction based on the line of sight velocity, we see again that most of our simulations are not playing when were looking and projection and that the Milky Way is just as planar as the simulations and effect and has a much broader distribution than it did in 3D. In general we are predicting that the Roman Space Telescope will likely observe satellites around analogs with the height of 60-135 and 50-80 will show lines of sight velocity. And now just to conclude, we have shown that the simulations are now reproducing, the distribution of galaxies around the house are no longer suffering from the missing satellite problem. In addition to that we look at the 3D spatial and kinematic distribution of galaxies and find that Milky Way like planes are rare but they exist. And the presence of the LMC is likely a key factor. Most likely because it's bringing in a lot of its own satellites and to the Milky Way satellite. And finally, some predictions for Milky Way planes in 2D for

observations with the Roman Space Telescope, but there's more work to be done to make a comparison in 2D between our simulations and observations. Thank you.

Thank you very much. The first question, and your work have you looked at the importance of the simulation with going larger? Sorry. What do you find, somebody else asked, what do you find is the correlation, having a companion with satellites and a plane, but it would be interesting to note, why are satellites being pushed to the plane?

Yes. Going off of the LMC results there. It seems like, there is another result from my paper that will be out next week and that is that even though we don't find instances, but we also find is at the very short-lived. That is part of the reason why it correlates so well with the presence of an L.E.D. only. They brought any satellites with it and it hasn't quite had enough time for them to dynamically dissociate from it. It's only really near that first center that we see these correlations. They quickly dissociate and that we don't see a huge correlation between the presence of an LMC at any point in its orbit and clarity.

Okay. There are many more questions on the slack. All of them look really interesting. I would encourage to move the discussion on there. We can move to the next. Thank you, Jenna. Thank you.

Our next speaker is **Scott Chapman**. He will tell us about uncovering clusters with the telescope. Whenever you are ready.

Scott: Great. I'm going to tell you about a massive galaxy protocluster in the early universe discovered by the South Pole telescope. What you are looking at here is our discovery data, very luminous and dense protocluster of galaxies that register at 4.3. And in the simulation of using these galaxies with using these conditions, but clearly what happens, what are known to be above 30 galaxies in the core, all merge very quickly within 500 mega years to turn into what seems to be the brightest cluster galaxy. Let's take a few steps back here. First of all, protoclusters are huge. They span a sort of degree scale regions with all of the stuff that will collapse down. Just by way of example I showed one of the protocluster structures registering at 2.9, Subaru. And also that very early on clusters or protoclusters have an inside out collapse formation structure as identified in simulations such as those. Finding very early quarters of protoclusters may be the best way to sign very massive structures forming. It's an experiment covering 2500 square degrees. Finding clusters of galaxies, of the important like shadows here shown. And discovered -- sort of order of 1,000 clusters, the ongoing experiment will extend that by an order of magnitude, 10,000 clusters and reaching now, but beyond red shift, we are clearly in the protocluster territory where we know longer have the high indicator of mature cluster. It does need to look for the galaxies themselves. The South pole telescope uncovered a bunch of lands millimeter galaxies resolved by ALMA with an optical lens in front. This is most of the thermal sources in the survey. We discovered along the way that a fraction of these, 10% might be a protocluster candidate. Instead of a gravitational lens galaxy consisting of on lens to galaxies packed this beam. We are talking at the threshold of 25 and the millimeter wavelength, the star formation, total star formation with ten solar masses per year, so extremely active protocluster. I've been flushing this out over the years and I found ten good candidates for protoclusters within the roughly 100-point sources in the survey, spanning redshifts of about 3-7. Most of them now confirmed with ALMA and multiple components. I want to point out that in these millimeter wavelengths of these things stand out like a sore thumb. I just showed one example here. There is not much of a background certainly. You are seeing filtered ripples there and then the point sources, there even extended at the beam, so they stand out from the other point surface, whereas the same region there are thousands of galaxies, but these, the source doesn't stand out dramatically in this case. It's a bit redder than most of the galaxies in the field, but it isn't particularly brighter. A survey, the source we saw in our title page is the brightest, but it gives us something to look for. There is no plausible lens in front and deep millimeter wave, 10 millimeters survey showed an over density of ride to satellites the larger regions, so larger scale structure. The brightest object has been studied in detail now, unequivocally a big protocluster structure. 33 very luminous galaxies. And the core region looks -- it allows us to make mass estimates. The star formation rate is around 17,000 solar masses per year and the core regions. The key results are that it's the most concentrated and highest rate system we know of, period, but certainly million solar mass per year cubed within the central regions. And it looks like a very massive halo greater than ten to the 13th solar masses at the red shift greater than 4 which looks to be consistent with the progenitor of a coma like cluster when you compare the tracks of

a collapsed core region with red shift. It looks, it has all of the signs of a progenitor of one of the most massive clusters we know of that presentation. When we look at the higher versions of this and are survey, 5.5-6.9 to give you an example and trying to compare the simulations, the contrast is even more severe. It is the range of expectations and star formation rate versus area in the sky or confirmation. There is clearly more OBs than predicted, even though they are extremely rare. There is only ten of them at this bright limit. There well in excess of recent modeling. What we expect at red shift for for these incredibly luminous protocluster systems. Characterizing the properties has been something we've been working on, they just published a paper on the stellar mass of some of the galaxies in the core. Their dynamical masses as well through the resolved properties. This is getting into the regime of interest for the enrollment space telescopes. There is just a montage of all the lines detected in the corporate start with bright lines with bright continuum and the cases gives us lots of information in the molecular luminosity functions. If we look over and the system, we run into immediate problems. The field is too small. The central pointing with the program, we have not enough characterize galaxy so you can see that both and the zoom of this one region with youth resources and on the right several sources received the velocity field and the C+ line on the right and that the image on the left. Typically a quite underwhelming, either undetected or barely detected a sources that are difficult to characterize. We have little information. In the stellar populations. The red shift of 69 structure, 25, but the small field size makes it difficult to cover the large extent of the system where we are finding the protocluster sources, prohibitive with HST. The integral field spectrograph looks at the structure and finds an over density. Also this giant blob and extended emission is often found in clustered sections. Interesting that they offset from the mass. Interesting thing is that we are, as I noted in the beginning, seeing the signs of early formation of the brightest cluster of galaxies and in the simulated sense and in this paper showing the total stellar mass already seen at red shift, 4.3 expected growth from the simulation and no more growth after that leads to a cluster galaxy which is much more massive than a sample of bright clusters at red shift one. You have 2 minutes. Just. Thank you. A few other tidbits, there is extended emission. The title streamer in the core gas, looking for AGN through a high transition. Rebecca is looking at this and trying to consolidate with that with x-ray observations. The simulations also suggest that these violent merger events may interject energy into the intracluster amount may be a heating mechanism for the simulation work. In summary I think the discovery of these protoclusters as possible due to the synergy between surveys... We just lost your audio.

I had one question myself to start with all the others type. You mentioned some models, but have you checked whether these clusters exist in models that early? For example?

That is what this -- sorry, you mean semianalytics? Yeah, the model is sort of the empirical model just pasting the functions together. And semianalytic models, the paper I referred to was in the multidark simulation come identifying counterparts and yet, they certainly struggled to find anything even close. The problem is the volumes typically. Struggling with the issue that these things are extremely rare from the point of view from the simulation versus the issue of whether there are recipes for star formation and such that mean you're never going to find them no matter how big of a volume you probe. There is a little bit of tension there. There does seem like the extrapolation from the models would not yield something as intense as the systems.

I guess that's a challenge for the models to try to address. There are no questions thus far. It's also late. We should probably just thanks Scott and conclude our session here. There will be now a poster session for one hour. I will leave it to the organizers at this point. If they want to take over with the posters. Because I think there is a live broadcast of the posters, if I recall correctly.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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